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Towards State-Based RT Analysis of FSM-SADFGs on MPSoCs with Shared Memory Communication

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I. INTRODUCTION

Scenario-aware-Data-Flow Graphs (SADFGs), first introduced in [5], achieve a good trade-off between expressiveness (allowing the expression of more dynamic behaviors than Synchronous Data-Flow [2] graphs (SDFGs)) and analyzability. Finite-State-Machine Scenario-Aware-Data-Flow (FSM-SADF) [4] graphs are a further simplification of the general SADF graphs. Both extend SDFGs with scenarios. In an FSM-SADF MoC a set of typical scenarios are pre-defined (through a finite state machine) for a specific SDF application. The SDF application reacts to every scenario in a different manner leading to more efficiency and better throughput. Fig. 1a shows an example FSM-SADF of an MPEG decoder as introduced by [5]. The vertices of the graph can be either kernels (VLD, MC, IDCT and RC) or detectors (FD). The solid edges are called *data* channels while the dashed edges are called *control* channels. Every input port of the kernels/detector in an FSM-SADF has a consumption rate and likewise each output port has a production rate. In each scenario, kernels can have different production and consumption rates. While general SADF graphs enable multiple scenario changes during one *iteration*¹ by allowing multiple scenario detectors, FSM-SADF graphs support only one detector per graph which simplifies the analysis of such models. Initial tokens are visualized by dots on the edges. For example the data channel from the kernel RC to the detector FD is initialized by three tokens, so that the detector can be executed three times before the kernel RC can execute to generate new tokens.

In this work, we extend our previous model-checking based real-time analysis approach in [1] for the analysis of timing bounds for FSM-SADFGs mapped on a shared memory multi-core architecture (1a). In our previous work only analysis of SDFGs was supported. We utilize timed automata (TA) as a common semantic model to represent worst-case execution times (WCET) of kernels, detectors and shared communication resource. The analysis model furthermore supports analysis of access protocols for buses, DMA, private local and shared memories of the MPSoC. For given FSM-SADFGs, MPSoC architecture, FSM-SADFG to MPSoC mapping, execution & communication times, and scheduling a network of TA can be generated. Using the UPPAAL model-checker, safe timing bounds of the FSM-SADFG MPSoC implementation can be provided. The closest work to ours was published recently in [3] where a translation from FSM-SADF graphs to TA was

¹An *iteration* is the minimum non-zero execution (i.e. at least one kernel has been executed) such that the initial state of the graph is obtained [1].

presented. In difference to our approach, the authors concentrated in their translation and analysis only on the FSM-SADF MoC and did not consider MPSoC mapping and resulting resource sharing aspects (i.e. contention on communication resources) in their work.

II. TRANSLATING FSM-SADF TO TIMED AUTOMATA

Model-checking SDFGs running on MPSoCs with shared communication resources was already described in [1]. In the following, only the relevant extensions will be described to enable model-checking FSM-SADF graphs. To support FSM-SADF, the detector and the FSM, determining the scenario in which the current SDF is executing, must be modeled as TA. The TA template of the detector and kernel (also called *actor* in the context of SDFGs) are similar, see Fig. 2a. Both TA can be split into three phases, the *read phase* in which all tokens are read from the channels, the *computation phase* where the read data gets processed, and the *write-phase* in which new tokens are written to the output ports. In addition to a kernel, the detector triggers a scenario switch at the end of the computation phase. In this case, an additional synchronization channel (Fig. 2a `updateScenario`) is used to trigger a state transition of the FSM TA, modeling the scenario switching, as shown in Fig. 2b. The global variable `scenario`, shown in Fig. 2b serves as an index for an array that holds the token rate configuration for each kernel in a specific scenario. Since the FSM is part of the *computation phase* of the detector, the execution time of the FSM is covered by the best-case and worst-case execution time of the detector. During the *write phase*, the detector produces control tokens but may also produce data tokens.

In model-checking, non-determinism can rapidly lead to a model with unmanageable state space (known as state-explosion problem). To avoid non-determinism in the FSM of an FSM-SADF graph, multiple possible successor states of an initial state can be abstracted to a single state as shown

Table I: I , P_0 , P_x are the states of the non-deterministic FSM [4] and become I , $P_{0/80}$, $P_{30/99}$ after abstracting to a deterministic FSM in Fig. 1b with best-case (BC) and worst-case (WC) rates.

Rate	Nondet. Scenarios			Det. Scenarios (BC/WC)		
	I	P_0	P_x	I	$P_{0/80}$	$P_{30/99}$
a	0	0	1	0	0 / 1	1 / 1
b	0	0	x	0	0 / 80	30 / 99
c	99	1	x	99	1 / 80	30 / 99
d	1	0	1	1	0 / 1	1 / 1
e	99	0	x	99	0 / 80	30 / 99

(a) FSM-SADF graph mapped on a dual core MPSoC. Kernels on the same core use local FIFOs, kernels mapped on different cores use FIFOs in shared memory.

(b) Top: original FSM [3], Bottom: deterministic abstracted FSM

Figure 1: FSM-SADF model of an MPEG-4 decoder [4] with an abstracted deterministic FSM

(a) A simplified TA template for the kernel (denoted by actor) and detector. `DetectorID` defines whether or not this TA is a detector.

(b) A TA template of the scenario FSM

Figure 2: Extensions to the TA representation of SDFGs

in Fig. 1b. This abstraction is valid since we are interested in getting the worst-case value of some timing constraint (such as *Period* or *end-to-end latency*). That is why the group of successor states of current state in the non-deterministic FSM can be abstracted in a single state representing worst-case-scenario state among this group. The same procedure could be done for the best-case the scenario state. This lead to a new deterministic FSM which describes the token rates in a more coarse way. To estimate which original scenario is the

worst and which one is the best, each one has to be analyzed individually as an SDF graph with a static token rate for this specific scenario. Note that also different execution times for every kernel/detector are used according to the current scenario (the execution time values were taken from [4]). This was done with the SDF2TA tool described in [1].

Table I shows that the channel b can be either 0 or 80 after the abstraction, while it had multiple rates ranging between 0, 40, 60 and 80 (see FSM in Fig. 1b) before. In Fig. 1b the state $P_{0/80}$ is equivalent to the original state P_{80} (see Tab. I) because in this scenario, the kernels RC and MC (see Fig. 1a) have to be executed most frequently and the highest amount of macro blocks need to be transferred between kernels. To get the best-case values, $P_{0/80}$ becomes equivalent to the original state P_0 (Tab. I) where most data channels transfer zero tokens and kernels are activated at most once per iteration. Kernels of the FSM-SADF that can work in different scenarios get notified of their scenario by control tokens produced by the detector. In case a kernel needs to be executed multiple times during one scenario iteration, it needs the proper amount of control tokens at its input port that can be consumed during each read phase. Control tokens are propagated from the detector to other kernels using the same shared resources that data tokens use. Therefore control tokens are modeled just like the data tokens only with a different token size.

In our example, we mapped the kernels, the detector and their communication channels implemented as FIFOs on a dual core architecture. The detector FD and the kernels RC and MC are mapped on *Core 1* while the kernels VLD and IDCT are mapped on *Core 2* as shown in Fig. 1a. The communication channels between kernels on the same core are mapped to a local memory, FIFOs for inter-core communication are mapped to shared memory.

In a first evaluation, we analyzed the worst-case end-to-end latency for the worst and the best scenario as show in Tab. I for $P_{0/80}$ and $P_{30/99}$. The end-to-end latency of our example was 8928 cycles for the best case scenario selection and 8969 cycles for the worst case scenario.

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